

Supplementary Material - Existing Theorem Proving in the Paper “Quantitative Performance Comparison of Various Traffic Shapers in Time-Sensitive Networking”

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Abstract

This document is a supplement material to make the paper “Quantitative Performance Comparison of Various Traffic Shapers in Time-Sensitive Networking” complete, including the existing work on Network Calculus-based analysis of different traffic shapers, i.e., TAS+CBS [2], CBS [1] of TSN. The service curve in [1] are extended to arbitrary number of AVB Class M_i ($i \in [1, n_{\text{CBS}}]$). The symbols are uniformly marked as in the comparison paper.

1 Service Curve for AVB Traffic under TAS+CBS Architecture

The service curve [2] is for multiple AVB Class M_i ($i \in [1, n_{\text{CBS}}]$) under the non-preemption mode with respectively (i) non-frozen and (ii) frozen credit during guard band (GB).

Theorem 1 (Service curve of Class M_i) Under the combined TAS+CBS architecture, the min-plus minimum service curve for AVB Class M_i ($i \in [1, n_{\text{CBS}}]$) under the non-preemption mode in an egress port is given by

$$\beta_{Q_i[M]}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \left[t - \frac{\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t)}{C} - \frac{c_{i[M]}^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right]_{\uparrow}^+, \quad (1)$$

where $M \in \{\text{NF}, \text{F}\}$ represents the behavior of credit during GB, and $\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ is the arrival curve with regard to credit frozen. In case of $M = \text{NF}$, i.e., (i) non-frozen credit during GB, $\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) = \alpha_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ is only related to higher priority TT traffic, while in case of $M = \text{F}$, i.e., (ii) frozen credit during GB, $\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) = \alpha_{\text{GB+TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ should additionally take guard band slots into account. $c_{i[M]}^{\max}$ is the upper bound of credit of Class M_i under cases of (i) non-frozen or (ii) frozen credit during GB, and given by Eq. (6) or Eq. (7).

Proof: Assume that $R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$ (resp. $R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$, $R_{\text{GB}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$) and $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t)$ (resp. $R_{[M]}^{*\text{TAS}}(t)$, $R_{\text{GB}}^{*\text{TAS}}(t)$) are the arrival and departure processes of AVB flows of Class M_i (resp. TT flows scheduled according to GCLs, guard bands) crossing through the output port h . Let $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be a time point when the queue Q_i of AVB Class M_i is backlogged, i.e., $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) < R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$. Then let us define $s = \sup\{u \leq t \mid c_i(u) = 0, R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(u) = R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(u), R_{[M]}^{*\text{TAS}}(u) = R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(u)\}$. This implies that $\forall u \in (s, t]$, the queue Q_i is non-empty or $c_i(u) < 0$. Otherwise, we can always find another $s < s' \leq t$ that satisfies $c_i(s') = 0$ and $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(s') = R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s')$. Moreover, it also implies that s is outside of TT window, guard bands duration. We define the duration $(s, t]$ the busy period of AVB Class M_i .

Then the interval $\Delta t = t - s$ can be decomposed by

$$\Delta t = \Delta t^- + \Delta t^+ + \Delta t^0,$$

where Δt^- (resp. Δt^+ , Δt^0) is the accumulated length of all periods where the credit is decreasing (resp. increasing, frozen). For the non-preemption integration mode, $\Delta t^- = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$ represents the transmission duration of AVB Class M_i , $\Delta t^0 = \Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}$ is caused by TT traffic windows, which equals to Δt_{TT} if credit is non-frozen during GB and to $\Delta t_{\text{TT}} + \Delta t_{\text{GB}}$ if credit is frozen during GB. Then we have

$$\Delta t^+ = \Delta t - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}. \quad (2)$$

The service curve for AVB traffic depends on the working mechanism of CBS. The credit $c_i(t)$ of AVB Class M_i increases at speed $idSl_i$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is waiting (during Δt^+ when high-priority frames in $Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ emission,

or guard band blocking), decreases at speed $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is transmitting (during $\Delta t^- = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$), and is not modified (frozen) during $\Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}$. Due to the definition of s , for $\forall u \in (s, t]$, the queue Q_i is not possible temporarily empty when $c_i(u) > 0$. Thus, there is no case that the credit of AVB Class M_i be reduced from some positive value P to 0 due to resets.

Then the variation of credit for AVB Class M_i during the time interval $\Delta t = t - s$ can be given by,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot sdSl_i + (t - s - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}) \cdot idSl_i,$$

Thus, it is obtained,

$$\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} = [(t - s - \Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}})idSl_i - c_i(t) + c_i(s)]/C. \quad (3)$$

Moreover, for the worst-case, the output frames of TT traffic during Δt can be given by

$$R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) - R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(s) = R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) - R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(s) = C \cdot \Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}} \leq R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) - R_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(s) \leq \alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t - s),$$

and thus,

$$\Delta t_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}} \leq \alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t - s)/C, \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t) = \alpha_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ if non-frozen credit during GB, and $\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}} = \alpha_{\text{TT+GB}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ if frozen credit during GB.

The service could only be supplied for AVB traffic M_i during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$ in the descent time Δt^- of credit. Then, over the interval $(s, t]$, considering $c_i(t) \leq c_{i[M]}^{\text{max}}$, $c_i(s) = 0$, Eq. (3), and Eq. (4), we have

$$R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) = C \cdot \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \geq idSl_i \left(t - s - \frac{\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t - s)}{C} - \frac{c_{i[M]}^{\text{max}}}{idSl_i} \right)$$

Since we have also $R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) = R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) \geq 0$ and $R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$ is a wide-sense increasing function, from which we derive

$$\begin{aligned} R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) &\geq R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) + idSl_i \left[t - s - \frac{\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t - s)}{C} - \frac{c_{i[M]}^{\text{max}}}{idSl_i} \right]_{\uparrow}^+ \\ &\geq \inf_{0 \leq s \leq t} \left\{ R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) + idSl_i \left[t - s - \frac{\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t - s)}{C} - \frac{c_{i[M]}^{\text{max}}}{idSl_i} \right]_{\uparrow}^+ \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the service curve $\beta_{Q_i[M]}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$ for AVB Class M_i is,

$$\beta_{Q_i[M]}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \left[t - \frac{\alpha_{[M]}^{\text{TAS}}(t)}{C} - \frac{c_{i[M]}^{\text{max}}}{idSl_i} \right]_{\uparrow}^+.$$

■

1.1 Bounding the Credit for AVB Traffic under TAS+CBS Architecture

Theorem 2 (Lower bound of credit for Class M_i) Let $l_{Q_i}^{\text{max}}$ be the maximal frame size of any flow crossing the AVB queue Q_i . Then, the credit $c_i(t)$ of Class M_i is lower bounded by,

$$c_i(t) \geq sdSl_i \cdot \frac{l_{Q_i}^{\text{max}}}{C} = c_i^{\text{min}}. \quad (5)$$

Proof: The credit of Class M_i will be decreased only when the frame of Class M_i is sent. In addition, since AVB frame cannot start to be transmitted when the credit is negative. Therefore, the condition for reaching the minimum credit happens when the maximum frame size $l_{Q_i}^{\text{max}}$ of Class M_i is just being sent while its credit drops exactly to 0. In such a case, the minimum credit equals to $c_i^{\text{min}} = l_{Q_i}^{\text{max}} \cdot sdSl_i / C$.

■

Before we start to prove the upper bound of credit, let us define some notations. Let $Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}} = \bigcup_{1 \leq j \leq i} \{Q_j\}$ denotes the same or higher priority AVB queues and $Q_{> i}^{\text{CBS}} = \bigcup_{i < j \leq n_{\text{CBS}}} \{Q_j\}$ denotes the lower priority AVB queues. Then for

$\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}^+, s \leq t$, the interval $[s, t]$ can be partitioned into several kinds of intervals: let $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s, t)$ and $\Delta t_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}(s, t)$ respectively denote the duration of emissions of frames from the queue Q_i and of high priority frames from the queue $Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$; $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, t)$ is the time slot reserved for TT traffic, *i.e.*, the duration where the gates of AVB queues are closed; $\Delta t_{\text{LP}}(s, t)$ is the duration where a frame in $Q_j \in \{Q_{>i}^{\text{CBS}}, Q_{\text{BE}}\}$ waits due to a lower priority frame in queue $Q_{>i}^{\text{CBS}}$ or Q_{BE} that is being transmitted cannot be preempted; $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, t)$ denotes the guard band duration where for all queues $Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ with $c_j > 0$ no frame can be sent, as there is no sufficient time available to transmit the entire frame before the next closing event; and $\Delta t_{\text{Other}}(s, t)$ is the interval except all the definitions above. Then we have $t - s = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s, t) + \Delta t_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}(s, t) + \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, t) + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}(s, t) + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, t) + \Delta t_{\text{Other}}(s, t)$.

Theorem 3 (Upper bound of credit for Class M_i) Let $l_{Q_{\text{BE}}}^{\text{max}}$ be the maximal frame size of BE flows. The credit $c_i(t)$ of Class M_i is upper bounded by,

(i) non-frozen credit during GB

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\text{min}} - l_{>i}^{\text{max}} - \sigma_i^{\text{GB}}}{\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C} = \bar{c}_i^{\text{max}}; \quad (6)$$

(ii) frozen credit during GB

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\text{min}} - l_{>i}^{\text{max}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C} = c_i^{\text{max}}. \quad (7)$$

where $l_{>i}^{\text{max}} = \max_{j \in [i+1, n_{\text{CBS}}]} \{l_{Q_j}^{\text{max}}, l_{Q_{\text{BE}}}^{\text{max}}\}$, c_j^{min} is the lower bound of credit of Class M_j from Theorem 2, and σ_i^{GB} and ρ_i^{GB} are the parameters of upper envelope related to guard band duration and satisfy for $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}^+, s \leq t$,

$$C \cdot \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, t) \leq \sigma_i^{\text{GB}} + \rho_i^{\text{GB}} \cdot (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, t)). \quad (8)$$

where σ_i^{GB} and ρ_i^{GB} will be discussed in Sect.1.2.

Proof: Let $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be a time point when AVB gates are in the open state, and $c_i(t) > 0$. Then let us define $s = \sup \{u \leq t \mid \forall Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(u) \leq 0\}$. It implies that $\forall u \in (s, t], \exists Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(u) > 0$, *i.e.* there always exists at least one queue in $Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ with some frame to send. Otherwise, we can always find another $s < s' \leq t$ that satisfies $\forall Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(s') \leq 0$. As it always exists one queue in $Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ with some frame to send, either it succeeds (there is a frame of Class M_i emission, or a high-priority frame in $Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ emission) or is blocked (non-preemption or guard band or TT traffic transmission). Thus $\Delta t_{\text{Other}}(s, t) = 0$ here. In the following, as s, t are fixed, the $\Delta t_X(s, t)$ will be simplified to Δt_X .

(i) *For the case of non-frozen credit during GB*

Consider first the evolution of the credit value of M_i between s and t . The credit $c_i(t)$ increases at speed $idSl_i$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is waiting (during $\Delta t_{<i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}} + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}$), decreases at speed $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is transmitting (during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$), is not modified when the gate of Q_i is closed during TT traffic transmission, and may be reduced from some positive value P to 0 due to resets. Thus the variation of $c_i(t)$ during $(s, t]$ is,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) = \Delta t_i \cdot sdSl_i + (\Delta t_{<i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}} + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}) \cdot idSl_i - P. \quad (9)$$

Since $\Delta t_{<i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}} + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} = t - s - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}$ and $P \geq 0$, Eq. (9) is modified into,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) \leq -\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}) \cdot idSl_i. \quad (10)$$

Let $c_{<i}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j(t)$ denote the sum of credits of AVB traffic with the priority higher than Class M_i . Consider three cases: first, at any instant between s and t either a frame of M_i uses the link, or a low priority frame blocks the link or during GB, the credit of each non-empty queue $Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ increases with speed $idSl_j$. Then the sum of credits $c_{<i}(t)$ increases at most at speed $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j$. Or a frame from class with higher priority than M_i is being sent. In this case $c_{<i}(t)$ decrease at least at speed $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C$ (all the classes from $Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ gain credit except one which loses credit). The last case is like for M_i , $c_{<i}(t)$ may decrease due to a set of resets. Then it is possible to upper bound the variation of $c_{<i}(t)$ between s and t ,

$$\begin{aligned} c_{<i}(t) - c_{<i}(s) &\leq (\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}} + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j + (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}} - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{\text{LP}} - \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right) \\ &= (\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}} + \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}) \cdot C + (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

By definition of s , it exists continuously some queue $Q_j \in Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}$ trying to send a frame. Hence there is at most one low priority frame that can get access to the link before s and go on transmission due to non-preemption. Thus

$$\Delta t_{\text{LP}} \cdot C \leq \max_{j \in [i+1, n_{\text{CBS}}]} \{l_{Q_j}^{\text{max}}, l_{\text{BE}}^{\text{max}}\} = l_{> i}^{\text{max}}.$$

Moreover, we assume that there exists σ_i^{GB} and ρ_i^{GB} which will be discussed in Sect. 1.2 such that $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}^+, s \leq t$,

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} \cdot C \leq \sigma_i^{\text{GB}} + \rho_i^{\text{GB}} \cdot (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}).$$

Thus, Eq. (11) is modified to obtain,

$$c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) \leq \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + l_{> i}^{\text{max}} + \sigma_i^{\text{GB}} + (t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}) \cdot \left(\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right). \quad (12)$$

Considering the system is assumed to be not overloaded, we have $\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j \leq C$. Thus, from Eq. (12)

$$t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}} \leq \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C - l_{> i}^{\text{max}} - \sigma_i^{\text{GB}}}{\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}. \quad (13)$$

Then from Eq. (13), Eq. (10) is modified to obtain,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) \leq idSl_i \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - l_{> i}^{\text{max}} - \sigma_i^{\text{GB}}}{\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}.$$

By definition of s , we have $c_{< i}(s) \leq 0$ and $c_i(s) \leq 0$ as well. Moreover, if c_j^{min} is the lower bound of credit of Class M_j , then $c_{< i}(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\text{min}}$ so to conclude,

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\text{min}} - l_{> i}^{\text{max}} - \sigma_i^{\text{GB}}}{\rho_i^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}.$$

(ii) *For the case of frozen credit during GB*

The proof is similar to the above process, except the difference of the evolution of credit of M_i during GB. The credit $c_i(t)$ increases at speed $idSl_i$ during $\Delta t_{< i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}$, decreases at speed $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$ during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$, and is not modified during guard band Δt_i^{GB} and TT traffic transmission Δt_{TT} . Then the variation of $c_i(t)$ during $(s, t]$ is upper bounded by,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) \leq -\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + (t - s - \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}) \cdot idSl_i. \quad (14)$$

Additionally, for the sum of credits $c_{< i}(t)$ of AVB traffic with the priority higher than Class M_i , it increases at most as speed $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j$ when the frame of M_i uses the link (during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$) or a low priority frame blocks the link (during Δt_{LP}),

$$\begin{aligned} c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) &\leq (\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j + (t - s - \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}} - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{\text{LP}}) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right) \\ &\leq \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + l_{> i}^{\text{max}} + (t - s - \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Similarly, considering the system is assumed to be not overloaded, we have $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j \leq C$. Thus, from Eq. (15)

$$t - s - \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}} \leq \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C - l_{> i}^{\text{max}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}. \quad (16)$$

Then from Eq. (16), Eq. (14) is modified to obtain,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) \leq idSl_i \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - l_{> i}^{\text{max}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}.$$

Thus, the upper bound of $c_i(t)$ is to conclude,

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\text{min}} - l_{> i}^{\text{max}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}.$$

■

1.2 Arrival Curve of TT/GB duration

In the following, we are interested to derive σ_i^{GB} and ρ_i^{GB} defined in Eq. (8) which is used for deriving credit upper bound of AVB Class M_i . They are parameters (burst and long-term rate) related to the upper envelope of accumulated bits in guard band duration $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, t)$ in any interval $[s, t]$. Additionally, note that σ_i^{GB} and ρ_i^{GB} are parameters defined based on $t - s - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, t)$ in Eq. (8). The following Theorem gives the upper envelope of the guard band defined in Eq. (8) in the form of the staircase function.

Theorem 4 The staircase upper bound on the GB duration defined from Eq. (8) for AVB Class M_i traffic for all $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is as follows,

$$\alpha_i^{\text{GB}}(t) = \max_{0 \leq n \leq N_{\text{TT}}-1} \{\alpha_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}(t - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(t))\}, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\alpha_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}(t - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(t)) = \sum_{m=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} C \left[\frac{t - o_{m,n}^{\text{TT}} + L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} + \sum_{p=n}^m L_p^{\text{TT}}}{T_{\text{GCL}} - \sum_{p=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} L_p^{\text{TT}}} \right]. \quad (18)$$

Proof: The purpose is to upper bound $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t)$ the number of $L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}$ in $[s, s+t]$. Introduce $\forall n : u_n = o_n^{\text{TT}} - L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}$. First, consider some u_n and $t \geq 0$, let $m = \max\{p \mid u_p < u_n + t\}$

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(u_n, u_n + t) \leq L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} + \dots + L_{m-1,i}^{\text{GB}} + L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} \leq \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} \mathbb{1}_{\{t > u_m - u_n\}} \quad (19)$$

Noticing that $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_m) = \sum_{p=n}^{m-1} L_p^{\text{TT}}$, Chasle's relation $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_n + t) = \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_m) + \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_m, u_n + t)$ and $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_m, u_n + t) \leq L_m^{\text{TT}}$ leads to

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(u_n, u_n + d) \leq \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} \mathbb{1}_{\{t - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_n + d) > u_m - u_n - \sum_{p=n}^m L_p^{\text{TT}}\}} \quad (20)$$

But any infinite sum on any expression $E(m)$, can be decomposed as a double sum using $m = m' + \epsilon N_{\text{TT}}$ with $m' = m \bmod N_{\text{TT}}$

$$\sum_{m=n}^{\infty} E(m) = \sum_{m'=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} \sum_{\epsilon=0}^{\infty} E(m' + \epsilon N_{\text{TT}}) \quad (21)$$

The system behavior is periodic, so $\forall m, u_{m+N_{\text{TT}}} = u_k + T_{\text{GCL}}$, $L_{m+N_{\text{TT}}}^{\text{TT}} = L_m^{\text{TT}}$, $L_{m+N_{\text{TT}},i}^{\text{GB}} = L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}}$, leading to, $\forall t$

$$\sum_{m=n}^{\infty} \mathbb{1}_{\{t > u_m - u_n - \sum_{p=n}^m L_p^{\text{TT}}\}} = \sum_{m'=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} \sum_{\epsilon=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{1}_{\{t > u_{m'+\epsilon N_{\text{TT}}} + \epsilon T_{\text{GCL}} - u_n - \sum_{p=n}^{m'+\epsilon N_{\text{TT}}} L_p^{\text{TT}} - \epsilon L_{\text{GCL}}^{\text{TT}}\}} \quad (22)$$

with $L_{\text{GCL}}^{\text{TT}} = \sum_{m=0}^{N_{\text{TT}}-1} L_m^{\text{TT}}$. Now, remark that $\forall t, J, P \in \mathbb{R}_+$, $P > 0$,

$$\left\lceil \frac{t - J}{P} \right\rceil^+ = \sum_{\epsilon=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{1}_{\{t > J + \epsilon P\}}. \quad (23)$$

Combining all leads to,

$$\sum_{m=n}^{\infty} L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} \mathbb{1}_{\{t > u_m - u_n - \sum_{p=n}^m L_p^{\text{TT}}\}} = \sum_{m=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}} \left\lceil \frac{t - (u_m - u_n - \sum_{p=n}^m L_p^{\text{TT}})}{T_{\text{GCL}} - L_{\text{GCL}}^{\text{TT}}} \right\rceil^+ \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} F_n(t) \quad (24)$$

Let $s \geq 0$, it exists o_n^{TT} such that $s \in [o_{n-1}^{\text{TT}}, o_n^{\text{TT}})$. If $s \in [o_{n-1}^{\text{TT}}, u_n]$, $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t) = \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(u_n, s+t)$. Using Eq. (20), Eq. (24), $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t) \leq F_n(s+t - u_n - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, s+t))$. From Chasle's relation and $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, u_n) \leq u_n - s$ comes $s - u_n - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, s+t) \leq -\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s+t)$. And since F_n is non decreasing, it leads to

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t) \leq F_n(t - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s+t)) \quad (25)$$

If $s \in [u_n, o_n)$, $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t) = \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(u_n, s+t) - (s - u_n)$. But for any x, y, z , $z \leq y$ $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(x, x+y) - z \leq \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(x, x+y-z)$, so $\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s+t) \leq \Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(u_n, u_n+t) \leq F_n(t - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_n+t))$. Consider now Δt_{TT} : from $s \in [u_n, o_n]$, $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_n+t) =$

Figure 1: Linear bound on staircase function

$\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, u_n + t)$, and from Chales's relation $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t) = \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, u_n + t) + \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n + t, s + t)$. Since $s \in [u_n, o_n]$, $s - u_n \leq o_n^{\text{TT}} - u_n = L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}$, then $\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n + t, s + t) \leq \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n + t, o_n + t) \leq L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}$. So, $-\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(u_n, u_n + t) \leq -\Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t) + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}}$, and since F_n is non decreasing,

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s + t) \leq F_n(t + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t)). \quad (26)$$

Last, to get rid of the position of s wrt o_n and u_n , one gets the maximum

$$\Delta t_i^{\text{GB}}(s, s + t) \leq \max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{F_n(t + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t))\} = \max_{0 \leq n \leq N_{\text{TT}} - 1} \{F_n(t + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} - \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t))\} \quad (27)$$

Last, we are looking for a bound on $C \cdot \Delta t_{\text{TT}}(s, s + t)$ and $t + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} - u_m + u_n = t + L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} - (o_m^{\text{TT}} - L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}}) + o_n^{\text{TT}} - L_{n,i}^{\text{GB}} = t - o_{m,n}^{\text{TT}} + L_{m,i}^{\text{GB}}$, leading to Eq. (18). ■

Lemma 1 (Linear bound on staircase function) Let $P \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $\{o_1, \dots, o_n\}, \{l_1, \dots, l_n\} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be two sets of non-negative values such that $o_1 \leq o_2 \leq \dots \leq o_n \leq P$. Let $f(t) = \sum_{m=1}^n l_m \lceil \frac{t - o_m}{P} \rceil$. Then for all $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$

$$f(t) \leq \rho t + \max \{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\}, \quad (28)$$

with $\sigma_k = \sum_{m=1}^k l_m - \rho o_k$, $\rho = \sum_{m=1}^n l_m / P$.

Proof: For any k , let $l_k : t \mapsto \sigma_k + \rho t$. Since $f(t + P) = f(t) + \rho P$, if $\forall u \in [0, P]$, $f(u) \leq l_k(u)$, then $f \leq l_k$. Notice that $l_k(o_k) = f(o_k)$, and $\forall u \in [o_k, o_{k+1}]$ $f(u) \leq \max \{l_k, l_{k+1}\}$ (cf. Fig. 1). So, $\forall u \in [0, P]$, $f(u) \leq \max_{k \in [1, n]} \{l_k(u)\}$. ■

1.3 CBS Shaping Curve for AVB traffic under TAS+CBS Architecture

Lemma 2 With the non-preemption mode, the strict service curve for TT traffic in an output port h is given by,

$$\beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t) = \min_{0 \leq n \leq N_{\text{TT}} - 1} \left\{ \sum_{m=n}^{n + N_{\text{TT}} - 1} \beta_{\text{TDMA}}(t + t_0, L_m^{\text{TT}}) \right\}, \quad (29)$$

where

$$\beta_{\text{TDMA}}(t, L) = C \cdot \max \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{t}{T_{\text{GCL}}} \right\rfloor L, t - \left\lceil \frac{t}{T_{\text{GCL}}} \right\rceil (T_{\text{GCL}} - L) \right\},$$

and

$$t_0 = T_{\text{GCL}} - L_m^{\text{TT}} - o_m^{\text{TT}} + o_{n-1}^{\text{TT}} + L_{n-1}^{\text{TT}}.$$

Proof: For the given GCL in an output port, there are N_{TT} number of TT windows in the GCL period T_{GCL} . Then the service for TT traffic can be taken as N_{TT} sets of periodic windows of known lengths and relative offsets.

If considering one set of periodic TT windows of length L within the GCL period T_{GCL} , its service in the port h is similar to the TDMA communication. In the worst-case, the service cannot be guaranteed for TT traffic during any time interval $0 \leq \Delta t < T_{\text{GCL}} - L$, but can be guaranteed of $C \cdot (\Delta t - T_{\text{GCL}} - L)$ in any time interval $T_{\text{GCL}} - L \leq \Delta t < T_{\text{GCL}}$. Then the service curve for periodic ST windows during Δt can be given by,

$$\beta_{\text{TDMA}}(\Delta t, L) = C \cdot \max \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{\Delta t}{T_{\text{GCL}}} \right\rfloor L, \Delta t - \left\lceil \frac{\Delta t}{T_{\text{GCL}}} \right\rceil (T_{\text{GCL}} - L) \right\}. \quad (30)$$

Then the service for all N_{TT} sets of periodic TT windows is derived from (30) as well as the relative offsets between two TT windows from different sets. Taking the n th ($n \in [0, N_{\text{TT}} - 1]$) TT window as the reference, we have that the first served frame is from the n th TT window during the backlogged period Δt . Assume that $o_{0,n}^{\text{TT}} = o_n^{\text{TT}} - o_{n-1}^{\text{TT}} - L_{n-1}^{\text{TT}}$ is the maximum idle time interval before the opening time of the i th window, then the service guaranteed for the n th set of TT windows is the curve in Eq. (30) shifted to the left with the positive value $T_{\text{GCL}} - L_n^{\text{TT}} - o_{0,n}^{\text{TT}}$,

$$\beta_{\text{TT},n,n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t) = \beta_{\text{TDMA}}^h(\Delta t + T_{\text{GCL}} - L_n^{\text{TT}} - o_{0,n}^{\text{TT}}, L_n^{\text{TT}}).$$

Moreover, for the other set of the m th ($m \in [n + 1, n + N_{\text{TT}} - 1]$) traffic windows, with the known of the relative offset $o_{m,n}^{\text{TT}} = o_m^{\text{TT}} - o_n^{\text{TT}}$ by considering the n th TT window as the benchmark, the service guaranteed for TT traffic in the j th set of windows can be given by shifting the curve in (30) to the left with the positive value $T_{\text{GCL}} - L_m^{\text{TT}} - o_{0,n}^{\text{TT}} - o_{m,n}^{\text{TT}}$,

$$\beta_{\text{TT},m,n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t) = \beta_{\text{TDMA}}^h(\Delta t + T_{\text{GCL}} - L_m^{\text{TT}} - o_m^{\text{TT}} + o_{n-1}^{\text{TT}} + L_{n-1}^{\text{TT}}, L_m^{\text{TT}}).$$

Note that $\beta_{\text{TT},m,n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t)$ equals to $\beta_{\text{TT},n,n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t)$ if $m = n$.

Thus if the n th TT window is as benchmark, the strict service for TT traffic is as follows after considering all N_{TT} sets of periodic TT windows,

$$\beta_{\text{TT},n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t) = \sum_{m=n}^{n+N_{\text{TT}}-1} \beta_{\text{TT},m,n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t).$$

Then the strict service curve for TT traffic in an output port h is the lower envelope of $\beta_{\text{TT},n}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t)$ by considering each TT windows in the GCL period as benchmark,

$$\beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t) = \min_{0 \leq n \leq N_{\text{TT}}-1} \{\beta_{\text{TT},n}^h(\Delta t)\}.$$

■

Theorem 5 Under the combined TAS+CBS architecture, the CBS shaping curve of Class M_i for the non-preemption mode is given by,

$$\sigma_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \cdot \left[t - \frac{\beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)}{C} \right]_{\uparrow}^+ + c_{i[M]}^{\max} - c_i^{\min}, \quad (31)$$

where $\beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(t)$ is given by the Lemma 2, and c_i^{\max} and c_i^{\min} are respectively the upper and lower bounds of credit of M_i given by Theorems 3 and 2.

Proof: For an arbitrary period of time Δt , the variation of credit during Δt satisfies

$$\Delta c_i = c_i(t + \Delta t) - c_i(t) = \Delta t^+ \cdot idSl_i + \Delta t^- \cdot sdSl_i = (\Delta t - \Delta t^0) \cdot idSl_i - \Delta t^- \cdot (idSl_i - sdSl_i). \quad (32)$$

In the best-case, the frozen duration $\Delta t^0 = \Delta t_{\text{TT}}$ is only related to TT windows, and has nothing to do with guard bands, for the non-preemption integration mode. Considering the strict service curve of TT traffic expressed in the Lemma 2, Δt_{TT} is limited by,

$$R_{\text{TT}}^{*\text{TAS}}(t + \Delta t) - R_{\text{TT}}^{*\text{TAS}}(t) = \Delta t_{\text{TT}} \cdot C \geq \beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t). \quad (33)$$

Moreover, Δt^- can be expressed by,

$$R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t + \Delta t) - R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) = \Delta t^- \cdot C, \quad (34)$$

and Δc_i satisfies the relationship as follows,

$$\Delta c_i \geq c_i^{\min} - c_{i[M]}^{\max}. \quad (35)$$

Due to non-decreasing function $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t)$ and using the expressions Eq. (33), Eq. (34), Eq. (35) and $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$, Eq. (32) is modified to obtain,

$$R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t + \Delta t) - R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \left[\Delta t - \frac{\beta_{\text{TT}}^{\text{TAS}}(\Delta t)}{C} \right]_{\uparrow}^+ + c_{i[M]}^{\max} - c_i^{\min}.$$

■

2 Service Curve for AVB Traffic under CBS Architecture

In this section, we will extend the service curve in [1] to multiple AVB Class M_i ($i \in [1, n_{\text{CBS}}]$).

Theorem 6 (Service curve of Class M_i) Under the individually CBS architecture, the min-plus minimum service curve for AVB Class M_i ($i \in [1, n_{\text{CBS}}]$) with the non-preemption mode in an egress port is given by

$$\beta_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \left[t - \frac{c_i^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right], \quad (36)$$

where c_i^{\max} is the upper bound of credit of Class M_i , and given by Eq. (40).

Proof: Let assume $R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$ and $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t)$ are the arrival and departure processes of AVB flows of Class M_i passing through the egress port h . Let $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be a time point when the queue Q_i of AVB Class M_i is backlogged, i.e., $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) < R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$. Then let us define $s = \sup\{u \leq t \mid c_i(u) = 0, R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(u) = R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(u)\}$. This implies that $\forall u \in (s, t]$, the queue Q_i is non-empty or $c_i(u) < 0$. Otherwise, we can always find another $s < s' \leq t$ that satisfies $c_i(s') = 0$ and $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(s') = R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s')$. We define the duration $(s, t]$ the busy period of AVB Class M_i .

Then the interval $\Delta t = t - s$ can be decomposed by $\Delta t = \Delta t^- + \Delta t^+$, where Δt^- (resp. Δt^+) is the accumulated length of all periods where the credit is decreasing (resp. increasing), and $\Delta t^- = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$ represents the transmission duration of AVB Class M_i . Then we have

$$\Delta t^+ = \Delta t - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}. \quad (37)$$

The credit $c_i(t)$ of AVB Class M_i increases at speed $idSl_i$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is waiting (during Δt^+ when high-priority frames in $Q_j \in Q_{<i}^{\text{CBS}}$ emission), and decreases at speed $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is transmitting (during $\Delta t^- = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$). Due to the definition of s , for $\forall u \in (s, t]$, the queue Q_i is not possible temporarily empty when $c_i(u) > 0$. Thus, there is no case that the credit of AVB Class M_i be reduced from some positive value P to 0 due to resets.

Then the variation of credit for AVB Class M_i during the time interval $\Delta t = t - s$ can be given by,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot sdSl_i + (t - s - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}) \cdot idSl_i,$$

Thus, it is obtained,

$$\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} = [(t - s)idSl_i - c_i(t) + c_i(s)]/C. \quad (38)$$

The service could only be supplied for AVB traffic M_i during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$ in the descent time Δt^- of credit. Then, over the interval $(s, t]$, considering $c_i(t) \leq c_i^{\max}$, $c_i(s) = 0$, and Eq. (38), we have

$$R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(s) = C \cdot \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \geq idSl_i \left(t - s - \frac{c_i^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right)$$

Since $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(s) = R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) - R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) \geq 0$ and $R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t)$ is a wide-sense increasing function, we then have

$$R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) \geq R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) + idSl_i \left[t - s - \frac{c_i^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right]^+ \geq \inf_{0 \leq s \leq t} \left\{ R_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(s) + idSl_i \left[t - s - \frac{c_i^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right]^+ \right\}.$$

Thus, the service curve $\beta_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t)$ for AVB Class M_i is,

$$\beta_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \left[t - \frac{c_i^{\max}}{idSl_i} \right]^+.$$

■

2.1 Bounding the Credit for AVB Traffic under CBS Architecture

Corollary 1 (Lower bound of credit for Class M_i) Let $l_{Q_i}^{\max}$ be the maximal frame size of any flow crossing the AVB queue Q_i . Then, the credit $c_i(t)$ of Class M_i is lower bounded by,

$$c_i(t) \geq sdSl_i \cdot \frac{l_{Q_i}^{\max}}{C} = c_i^{\min}. \quad (39)$$

Proof: The proof is same to the Theorem 2.

Theorem 7 (Upper bound of credit for Class M_i) Let $l_{Q_{BE}}^{\max}$ be the maximal frame size of BE flows. The credit $c_i(t)$ of Class M_i is upper bounded by,

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\min} - l_{>i}^{\max}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C} = c_i^{\max}. \quad (40)$$

where $l_{>i}^{\max} = \max_{j \in [i+1, n_{\text{CBS}}]} \{l_{Q_j}^{\max}, l_{Q_{BE}}^{\max}\}$, c_j^{\min} is the lower bound of credit of Class M_j from Corollary 1.

Proof: Let $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be a time point $c_i(t) > 0$. Then we define $s = \sup \{u \leq t \mid \forall Q_j \in Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(u) \leq 0\}$. It implies that $\forall u \in (s, t], \exists Q_j \in Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(u) > 0$, i.e. there always exists at least one queue in $Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}$ with some frame to send. Otherwise, we can always find another $s < s' \leq t$ that satisfies $\forall Q_j \in Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}, c_j(s') \leq 0$. Since there always exists one queue in $Q_{\leq i}^{\text{CBS}}$ with some frame to send, either it succeeds (there is a frame of Class M_i emission, or a high-priority frame in $Q_j \in Q_{< i}^{\text{CBS}}$ emission) or is blocked (non-preemption from lower priority traffic).

The credit $c_i(t)$ increases at speed $idSl_i$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is waiting (during $\Delta t_{< i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}$), decreases at speed $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$ when the frame in the queue Q_i is transmitting (during $\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}$), and may be reduced from some positive value P to 0 due to resets. Since $t - s = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{< i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}$, the variation of $c_i(t)$ during $(s, t]$ is then upper bounded by,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) = \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot sdSl_i + (\Delta t_{< i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}) \cdot idSl_i - P \leq -\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + (t - s) \cdot idSl_i. \quad (41)$$

Additionally, let $c_{< i}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j(t)$ denote the sum of credits of AVB traffic with the priority higher than Class M_i . At any instant between s and t either a frame of M_i uses the link, or a low priority frame blocks the link, the credit of each non-empty queue $Q_j \in Q_{< i}^{\text{CBS}}$ increases with speed $idSl_j$. Then the sum of credits $c_{< i}(t)$ increases at most at speed $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j$. Or a frame from class with higher priority than M_i is being sent. In this case $c_{< i}(t)$ decrease at least at speed $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C$. Or $c_{< i}(t)$ may decrease due to a set of resets,

$$\begin{aligned} c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) &\leq (\Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} + \Delta t_{\text{LP}}) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j + (t - s - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} - \Delta t_{\text{LP}}) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right) \\ &\leq \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C + l_{> i}^{\max} + (t - s) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C \right). \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Considering the system is assumed to be not overloaded, we have $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j \leq C$. Thus, from Eq. (42)

$$t - s \leq \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - \Delta t_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}} \cdot C - l_{> i}^{\max}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}. \quad (43)$$

Then from Eq. (43), Eq. (41) is modified to obtain,

$$c_i(t) - c_i(s) \leq idSl_i \frac{c_{< i}(t) - c_{< i}(s) - l_{> i}^{\max}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}.$$

By definition of s , we have $c_{< i}(s) \leq 0$ and $c_i(s) \leq 0$ as well. Thus, we conclude,

$$c_i(t) \leq idSl_i \cdot \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} c_j^{\min} - l_{> i}^{\max}}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} idSl_j - C}. \quad \blacksquare$$

2.2 CBS Shaping Curve for AVB traffic under CBS Architecture

Theorem 8 Under the individually CBS architecture, the CBS shaping curve of Class M_i for the non-preemption mode is given by,

$$\sigma_{Q_i}^{\text{CBS}}(t) = idSl_i \left[t + \frac{c_i^{\max} - c_i^{\min}}{idSl_i} \right], \quad (44)$$

where c_i^{\max} and c_i^{\min} are respectively the upper and lower bounds of credit of M_i given by Theorems 7 and Corollary 1.

Proof: For an arbitrary period of time Δt , the variation of credit during Δt satisfies

$$\Delta c_i = c_i(t + \Delta t) - c_i(t) = \Delta t^+ \cdot idSl_i + \Delta t^- \cdot sdSl_i = \Delta t \cdot idSl_i - \Delta t^- \cdot (idSl_i - sdSl_i), \quad (45)$$

where Δt^- can be expressed by,

$$R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t + \Delta t) - R_{Q_i}^{*\text{CBS}}(t) = \Delta t^- \cdot C, \quad (46)$$

and Δc_i satisfies the relationship as follows,

$$\Delta c_i \geq c_i^{\min} - c_i^{\max}. \quad (47)$$

Due to non-decreasing function $R_{Q_i}^{*CBS}(t)$ and using the expressions Eq. (46), Eq. (47) and $sdSl_i = idSl_i - C$, Eq. (45) is modified to obtain,

$$R_{Q_i}^{*CBS}(t + \Delta t) - R_{Q_i}^{*CBS}(t) \leq idSl_i \left[\Delta t + \frac{c_i^{\max} - c_i^{\min}}{idSl_i} \right].$$

■

References

- [1] J. A. R. Azua, and M. Boyer, "Complete modelling of AVB in network calculus framework," in *Proc. of the 22nd Int. Conf. on Real-Time Networks and Systems*, 2014.
- [2] L. Zhao, P. Pop, Z. Zheng, H. Daigmore, and M. Boyer, "Latency Analysis of Multiple Classes of AVB Traffic in TSN with Standard Credit Behavior using Network Calculus," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, in press, 2020.